

Re-thinking Politics and Ethno-religious Issues in Contemporary Nigeria

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Abstract

Politics is regarded as the art of governance; and has to do with acquisition and use of power. In Africa, nay Nigeria, politics is still regarded as a “dirty game” via which the ultimate goal is to secure power at all cost. Ethnicity and religion are seen as suitable platforms for mass mobilisation in the hands of the political elite. This is simply because of their all-embracing and emotive nature. However, due to some correlation between political and socio-economic development, the evolving political underdevelopment through a culture of undemocratic party politics characterised by monetary inducements, vote-buying, violence, and the weaponisation of ethno-religious differences has promoted a dysfunctional social force, which has equally produced a degeneration that is antithetical to national development and nation-building in Nigeria. This paper, thus, interrogates the ethno-religious issues that have characterised politics in Nigeria since 1999, when the current Fourth Republic was birthed. The paper relies heavily on secondary sources of historical data. The paper, therefore, concludes by recommending that, building and maintaining state institutions that are capable of regulating the conduct of the political elite be established, among others.

Keywords: Development, Ethnicity, Nigeria, Politics, Religion

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1. Introduction

Politics is the process of choosing public leaders that pilot and manage the affairs, especially the economy and security of a country via periodic elections.¹ Globally, security and economy are the crucial issues on which manifestoes of political parties are built.² These are the avenues for pursuing the welfare of the people. However, since 1999, when this Fourth Republic was birthed, Nigeria has not been classified a one of the developed or promising countries in the world. Regrettably, the inability

1. See Olufemi Oyedele, “Issue-based Politics and Economic Development in Nigeria”. Available @<https://punchng.com/issue-based-politics-and-economic-development-in-nigeria> (accessed 15-11-22).

2. For more on this, see Oyedele, Issue-based Politics”.

of the political class with a view to harnessing both the human and material resources for the sole purpose of nation-building and national development has made Nigeria to be “the sleeping giant of Africa”.³

Further, African identity is formulated by religion and ethnicity, both of which affect politics.⁴ According to Falola, ethnicity can be linked to prebendalism.⁵ This is a culture of using power to steal money from public purse. Here, the ethnic leader becomes the distributor of largesse, got from the state, to an army of followers drawn from among members of his ethnic group. Obviously, the answer lies in seeking power; once in power, the accumulation of wealth is seen in collective terms. Put differently, the corrupt leader steals not just for himself, but on behalf of his ethnic group. He, therefore, presents his success and wealth as the embodiment of his ethnicity. This would lead to sharing part of what he steals, that is, giving back to some of his people.⁶ More importantly, members of his group have access to jobs and privileges through this corrupt leader. Hence, corruption is justified by the necessity of meeting ethnic needs and responsibility at the expense of the Nigerian state.

Moreover, Islam and Christianity are two established global religions in Nigeria. Indeed, both have undermined indigenous religions and controlled and are still controlling much of the political and social spaces.⁷ The spread of both religions is uneven, thereby making religion to be sometimes coterminous with ethnic identities. Islam is dominant in the north, and competes with Christianity in the South as well as in the Middle Belt. Similarly, a North-South regional divide is seen as the Muslim-Christian divide. The two foreign imposed religions compete for space, converts and political domination. Leaders of both religions employ the style and language of politics in their quest for propaganda, control of converts, and the prevention of each other from dominating the political space. In fact, in their interactions, everything becomes political. Indeed, religion, like ethnicity has become a source of mobilization for the political gladiators. Islam, Christianity and ethnicity are manipulated by key political actors with a view to obtaining and consolidating this power. Rivalries among states and religions may, at the same time, be opportunities for leading political actors to settle their scores. These two totems of ethnicity and religion have impacted negatively on nation-building, national cohesion and development in Nigeria since the beginning of the Fourth Republic in 1999.

The objective of this paper is to examine how ethnicity and religion have impacted politics negatively, and the resultant effects on nation-building and national development in Nigeria since 1999. In doing this, the paper is structured into five sub-topics. One is the introductory aspects; two, creation, manifestation and consolidation of ethnic-politics in Nigeria; three, religious identity and politics; four, Nigeria and ethno-religious politics; and finally, conclusion and policy recommendations.

3. See R.T. Akinyele, “Ethnicity, Religion and Politics in Nigeria”, in R.A. Olaniyan (ed.), *The Amalgamation and its Enemies: An Interpretive History of Modern Nigeria* (Ile-Ife: OAU Press, Ltd., 2003), 123.

4. See Toyin Falola, *The Toyin Falola Reader on African Culture, Nationalism, Development and Epistemologies* (Austin, Texas: Pan-African University Press, 2018), 421.

5. See Falola, *The Toyin Falola Reader*, 423. For more details on Prebendalism, see Oladapo Fafowora, “The challenges of Democracy in Contemporary Nigeria”, in Olutayo C. Adesina (ed.), *Nigeria in the Twentieth Century: History, Governance and Society* (Ibadan: Connel Publications, 2017), 162-164.

6. See Falola, *The Toyin Falola Reader*, 424

7. For more information on this, see Falola, *The Toyin Falola Reader*, 480-483.

2. Origins, Manifestation and Consolidation of Ethnic Politics in Nigeria

Generally, ethnicity has become a complex phenomenon associated with religious, political, juridical and other social aspects of human beings.⁸ Indeed, ethnicity has become a big issue in African politics. How did this phenomenon of ethnicity start in Nigeria? Nnoli argues that, ethnicity as a concept, had a colonial origin, and its function was tied to the nature and purpose of colonisation.⁹ He submits further that, the colonialists changed the material ways of the Africans by forcing them to participate in colonial economy dominated by the profit motive, via “forced labour, taxation, the introduction of new currencies, and the creation of artificial scarcity, low wages, low prices for cash crops, and costly social services”.¹⁰ These policies later caused the population to abandon their former economic activities to enter the new system dominated by foreign ownership of the major means of production, distribution and exchange.¹¹ The colonialists, in order to justify their racist view of the Africans, began to categorise African linguistic groups as tribes; and attributed to them differences in culture and way of life.¹² The colonialists began separating these linguistic groups from one another, especially in the residential areas.¹³ For instance, in northern Nigeria, the British separated the Hausa-Fulani from the Southerners, by establishing strangers’ quarters (*Sabongari*).

Moreover, Melson and Wolpe argue that, the origins of ethnicity in Nigeria dates back to the closing decades of the colonial era, when the current linguistic and cultural identities began to emerge.¹⁴ According to the duo, the period was characterised by the fusion and development of communal boundaries.¹⁵ This was the time when the idea of an Igbo nation, Hausa-Fulani identity and a Yoruba race began to manifest. Obviously, the first noticeable manifestation of this was the formation of cultural unions and improvement associations in the colonial urban centres. The reason for the establishment of these associations was the improvement of the welfare of their members. These associations emulated each other, especially in awarding scholarships and erecting of community schools.¹⁶ However, some scholars are of the opinion that the politicisation of the cultural unions/associations birthed the beginning of ethnic politics in Nigeria.

More importantly, the Nigerian Youth Movement (NYM) was one of the earliest political parties in Nigeria, the origins of which can be traced to 1934. It was a broad based and nationalistic in nature, especially when you take into consideration, its membership and spread. The rivalry among its leadership sent this movement packing. Dr. Nnamdi Azikiwe was alleged to have infused ethnic sentiment into the movement

8. For more information on this, see Akinyele, “Ethnicity, Religion”, 124.

9. See, for instance, Okwudiba Nnoli, *Ethnic Politics in Nigeria* (Enugu: Fourth Dimension, 1978), 1-10. See also, Frantz Fanon, *Toward the African Revolution* (New York: Grove Press, 1966), 31-35.

10. See Nnoli, *Ethnic Politics*, 1-2.

11. Nnoli, *Ethnic Politics*.

12. See Nnoli, *Ethnic Politics*, 2.

13. Nnoli, *Ethnic Politics*.

14. See Robert Melson and Howard Wolpe, “Modernisation and the Politics of Communalism: A Theoretical Perspective”, in R. Melson and H. Wolpe, (eds.), *Nigeria: Modernisation and the Politics of Communalism* (East Lansing: Michigan State University Press, 1971), 22.

15. See Melson and Wolpe, “Modernisation and the Politics”.

16. For instance, see Akinyele, “Ethnicity, Religion”, 126.

simply because of the rivalry between him and Earnest Ikoli. Ikoli, the proprietor of the *Daily Service* newspaper had a running battle with Zik because his newspaper had begun to overshadow the *West African Pilot* owned by Zik.¹⁷ This professional rivalry impacted negatively on the relationship between the two. Zik supported Samuel Akinsanya (a Yoruba man) against Ikoli for the post of the President of the movement in 1941.¹⁸ However, Obafemi Awolowo and H.O. Davies pitched their camp with Ikoli, who finally won the election. Zik believed that his candidate lost the election because he was not a Yoruba man.¹⁹ Therefore, himself and his Igbo supporters left the movement. It must be noted here that the defeated man, Samuel Akinsanya was an Ijebu man, just like Obafemi Awolowo, while Ikoli was an Ijaw man.

In addition, Zik was elected as president of the Igbo State Union in 1948.²⁰ In his acceptance speech, he affirmed the right of the Igbo to lead other ethnic groups in Africa. Scholars have argued that, this singular act stained the then cordial relationship existing among the cultural groups; and led many of them, like the Ijaw, Edo, among others, to found their own ethnic unions for protection.²¹ This is the reason the establishment of *Egbe Omo Oduduwa* in 1948 was interpreted “as a declaration of war by a cross-section of the Igbo in Lagos”.²² Indeed, personal rivalry between Awolowo and Zik created the fertile ground for the ethnic suspicion that appeared to have influenced the outcome of the 1952 election. Zik did go back to the East and used the same ethnic sentiment against Dr. Eyo Ita. This annoyed Eyo Ita’s kinsmen, who began to look for a separate identity for themselves.

In addition, the Action Group (AG), Northern Peoples Congress (NPC) and Northern Element Progressive Union (NEPU) were founded to contest election under the 1951 Constitution. The AG and NPC sprang out from the cultural unions of the Yoruba and Hausa- Fulani people, by name *Egbe Omo Oduduwa* and *Jamiya Mutaren Arewa*, respectively.²³ Furthermore, the first truly national party formed in 1944 was the National Council of Nigeria and the Cameroons (NCNC) founded by Dr. Azikiwe on the initiative of the Nigerian Students’ Union in 1944. Zik became the President of the party after the demise of Herbert Macaulay in 1946. By 1951, the NCNC had become essentially an Igbo party, thereby signifying the triumph of ethnicity over the attempt to build a virile and united country. Regional considerations took over national interests. The Lyttleton Constitution of 1954 brought about the regionalisation of the sources of wealth and power. With the independence drawing near, the ethnic minorities believed that they would be excluded from power, except the Nigerian map was redrawn with a view to shedding their minority toga. The

17. Akinyele, “Ethnicity, Religion”.

18. Akinyele, “Ethnicity Religion”.

19. For more information on this, see R.J. Akinyele, “The Growth of Nationalism and the Political Evolution of Nigeria”, in Jide Osuntokun and Ayodeji Olukoju (eds.), (Citation incomplete in source text, continuing with footnote number in source)

20. See T.N. Tamuno “Separatist Agitations in Nigeria since 1914”, *Journal of Modern African Studies*, Vol. 8, No. 4, (1970), 566-568.

21. See J.S. Coleman, *Nigeria: Background to Nationalism* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1963), 347.

22. Akinyele, “Ethnicity, Religion”, 127.

23. Akinyele, “The Growth of Nationalism”, 291. See also, Oluwatoyin Oduntan, *Power, Culture and Modernity in Nigeria: Beyond the Colony* (London and New York: Routledge, 2018), 144-150.

Willink Commission of Enquiry was established to consider the minority issues. The commission did not recommend the creation of any new state in 1958.

However, the fear of ethnic domination was heavily politicised, to the extent that, each of the dominant regional parties formed an alliance with the minority party of their regions in order to be successful at the polls.²⁴ This issue could not be resolved in The Resumed London Constitutional Conference in 1959, and was carried over to 1960, when the country became independent. From 1960 till date, political aspirants still portray themselves as ethnic champions. The pattern of voting still reflects ethnic, religious, and regional bias.²⁵

3. Religious Identity and Politics

Religion constitutes an integral part of African politics. On 29th May, 1999, the Fourth Republic came into being. There was a First Republic, starting from 1960–1966, a Second, 1979–1983. The Third Republic was aborted. It can be said that it was the abortion of the Third Republic that birthed the Fourth Republic. More importantly, the elections of 1998–1999 did not produce many peculiarities of their own, owing to the fact that, the important variables that determined them had long been in existence, namely; “ethnicity, religion, competition over resource sharing, minority and communal marginalization, personality and ego contests, and the prominent role of money”.²⁵ In all this, the role of Islam has been constant in some aspects and changing in others. Just like ethnicity, it is a weapon of manipulation used by the political power seekers. Falola sees it this way:

If many politicians and people see in Islam a political ideology and tool, the non-Muslims seek the means to counter the power of Islam, to use ethnicity as a source of identity to mobilise themselves against possible Islamic domination, and to advocate secular institutions as the only available option to manage a modern country.²⁶

To allay the fears of being dominated by Muslims, the strategies employed by non-Muslims have been to use primordial identities and ethnicity with a view to radicalising Christianity or politicising the congregations so that they will not take away Christianity from politics. They also do promote a regional concept of the South against the North; the promotion of the spread of Western education and secular institutions. This includes an insistence on a modern judiciary, using English law; affirm Nigeria

24. The source text here ends with footnote number 25, which appears to be missing its content. I am adding a placeholder footnote.

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24. See for instance, “Report of the Commission appointed to enquire into the Fears of Minorities and the means of allaying them”, London, H.M.S.O., 1958. See also, R.T. Akinyele, States Creation in Nigeria. The Willink Report in Retrospect”, *African Studies Review*, Vol. 39, No. 2, Sept. (1996), 71–94.

24. See Richard Bourne, *Nigeria: A New History of a Turbulent Century* (London: Zed Books, 2015), 250–253.

25. See Falola, *The Toyin Falola Reader*; 469.

26. Falola, *The Toyin Falola Reader*. On religion in politics in Nigeria, see also, John Hunwick, *Religion and National Integration in Africa: Islam, Christianity and Politics in the Sudan and Nigeria* (Evanston: Northwestern University Press, 1992); Habib Boular, *Islam: The Fear and the Hope* (London: Zed, 1990).

as a secular state; and sponsor the elections of non-Muslims into power.²⁷ Religion is a source of mobilisation for the political gladiators. Immediately a political candidate defines himself as a Muslim and his opponent happens to be a Christian, politics can begin to gain the colouration of religious crisis. For instance, since the beginning of this Fourth Republic, in the North, many politicians have turned to Islam for power legitimisation. There have been rivalries with Christians and attempts to impose the Sharia over a larger region. Indeed, these attempts have radicalised the Christian Association of Nigeria to contest all religious symbols and what it claims as efforts to use Islam to dominate politics.²⁸ Obviously, the Northern political elite have continued to profit from Islam, using its symbols as political ideology with a view to uniting the region against the South; and to mobilise their different constituencies.

More importantly, there is a growing awareness that religion has become as disruptive as ethnicity to the peace and progress of Nigeria since the late 1970s.²⁹ This is owing to the mixing of politics with religion. Olaniyi avers thus:

... for everything in Nigerian politics, there is an arm of religion and for even sinister encounter in religion, politics looms at the corner and for all evils ever wrested by either the highly or lowly placed Nigerian, God is without and material acquisition within.³⁰

The connection between religion and politics is old just like the human society. For example, in most pre-colonial African societies, the king was often the chief priest or the head of all religions in his kingdom.³¹ In Nigeria, we had the cases of the old Oyo, Benin and Karnem Borno empires. They all suggest that religion was then used to boost the image and power of the king who was believed to be a semi-divine personality. At this very period, African traditional religion played a very limited role in African politics. Today, the reverse is the case in Nigeria. Religion has become totemic as far as politics is concerned. As a result of this, the loyalty of the people to Islam and Christianity remains stronger than the loyalty to Nigeria; and this has stalled national cohesion and nation-building in Nigeria since 1999, when this Fourth Republic started.

4. Nigeria and Ethno-religious Politics

In Nigeria, since 1940s, the ambition of the political actors has been to establish a strong nation-state and a federal political system. However, this is yet to be a reality, owing to the fact that, the nature of political competition and a politicised economy has made access to political power the most lucrative job. As discussed earlier, the trend toward political division began during the colonial period as the British policies encouraged ethnic divisions, the nationalist movement broke into pieces; and the

27. For more on ethno-religious politics in Nigeria, see A.O. Adesoji, "Restoring Peace or Waging War: Security Agencies Management of Ethno-religious Uprisings in Nigeria". *African Security Review*, 19: 3, (2010), 2-14; M.H. Kukah, *Religion, Politics and Power in Northern Nigeria* (Ibadan: Spectrum, 1993).

28. See for instance, Niels Kast-felt, *Religion and Politics in Nigeria: A Study in Middle Belt Christianity* (London: British Academy Press, 1994).

29. See *The Comet*, 31st October, 2001, 16.

30. See Taiye Olaniyi, cited in Akinyele, "Ethnicity, Religion", 128.

31. See Akinyele, "Ethnicity, Religion".

federal constitution of 1954 gave full rein to the competition among the three big regions, namely, the North, the West and the East.³²

Consequently, Nigeria got its nationhood from Britain in 1960 as a weakened and divided society. Nigeria inherited many legacies of colonial rule. This includes, a Westminster parliamentary system;³³ complicated ethnic and regional divisions that led to bitter rivalries; competition between traditional and educated elite; an export-oriented economy; and a public, rather than an economic elite that needed the control of state institutions to sustain and consolidate itself. Indeed, very rapidly, regionalism and political competition led to the fall of the First Republic, the incursion of military in government, and a civil war, all within the first decade of independence.³⁴ Further, the 1970s witnessed an oil boom which boosted the economy rapidly, producing a temporary military disengagement that birthed the short-lived Second Republic.³⁵ The military regimes of Muhammed Buhari and Ibrahim Babangida ruled Nigeria for most of the 1980s; and those of Babangida and Sanni Abacha in the 1990s.

However, the 1990s could be regarded as the worst decade in the modern history of Nigeria. The dictatorial tendencies of General Sanni Abacha re-defined the patrimonial state by incorporating all the worst excesses of power and corruption, without any regard for accountability; and domestic or international opinions. Abacha later died and was succeeded by Abdulsalam Abubakar in 1998. Abubakar announced a transition time-table of less than a year, from September 24, 1998 to May 29, 1999. A large number of political parties, twenty-six, were formed, but only nine got official recognition and only three became very active; some scholars have criticised the high number of political parties, while some have seen them as a true expression of the democratic spirit. The two views can be misleading. The participants were not expecting a political space with many political parties or were they fostering democracy. Rather, a political party enabled its founder and key executives to justify their claim to representing religious or ethnic interests, with a view to creating opportunities to negotiate with fellow politicians so that power can be distributed to as many of them as possible.

Since the beginning of this Fourth Republic, the political actors have carefully schemed political discourses and campaigns less on policies and more on personality. The major actors control the newspaper pages, posing both as representatives of various interest groups; and as nationalists. Today they would talk as true Muslims or Christians; tomorrow as defenders of ethnicities; and the next day as “true federalists”.³⁶ They do this through the extensive use of money to woo opponents and buy votes.

Money has become one of the major determinants in the contest. Politics in Nigeria favours those who have it in abundance or those who have wealthy sponsors or “god fathers” as the case may be. Since most wealthy Nigerians have accumulated

32. On history of Nigeria, see Toyin Falola, *The History of Nigeria* (Greenport C.I: Westview, 1999).

33. This system failed and later replaced with an American-style presidential constitution in 1979; this was also adopted in 1999.

34. See Falola, *The Toyin Falola Reader*, 470-471.

35. Falola, *The Toyin Falola Reader*.

36. For instance, see Ehimika Ifidon “Ethnicity, Differential Citizenship and the Problem of Nation-building”, in R.A. Olaniyan (ed.), *The Amalgamation and its Enemies*, 167-182; Toyin Falola, “The Fault Lines of Politics: Majority-Minority Identities in Nigerian Affairs”. First Eminent Personality Public Lecture delivered at Samuel Adegboyege University, Ogwa, Edo State, December 9, 2016.

wealth via connection to state power, politics in Nigeria tends to favour those who have previously held power, such as retired military officers or politicians that have held political offices or served as civil servants.³⁷ For example, Chiefs Olusegun Obasanjo, Olu Falae and Alex Ekwueme in 1999, Obasanjo served as head of state in the 1970s, Ekwueme as Vice-President during the Second Republic in the 1980s; and Falae as the Head of the Federal Civil Service and Secretary to the Babangida Military regime in the 1980s.

In the above analysis, one must consider the power of Islam and Christianity. Equally, there are other identities and social classes that affect elections and politics in a way that oppose or reinforce the Islamic elements. Of equal importance are issues that divide people and over which they need to vigorously compete. Primordial loyalties based on ethnicity, community and religion may transcend the loyalty to the Nigerian state, constitution, law and order. Also, primordial loyalties may strengthen or undermine the force of Islam. As a matter of fact, the South is more afraid of the North. Since independence, the North has produced the majority of the country's leaders, leading to the political concept of "northern hegemony".³⁸ The British colonialists bequeathed a northern region bigger than the east and west combined. After independence, the political elite in the North used the army to control power and distribute resources to themselves. According to Falola, in the 1990s, a number of northern intelligentsia was developing a political theory of domination that the East should control trade, the West, the civil service, and the North, the political power.³⁹ Also, a tiny Islamic intelligentsia was soliciting a possible end to the definition of the country as a secular state. When the 1993 presidential election was cancelled, the only explanation the southern elite could adduce was that, it was another example of northern oligarchy; and the conflict became one of overcoming the fears and effects of northern domination.

This fear of domination led to suggestions on zoning formula, an arrangement in which each region would produce the country's president in a rotational arrangement. This consideration has to do with satisfying the political class rather than the economic costs that would be consumed in the process, thereby slowing down development; and resulting in the inability to have the necessary resources to transform the rural areas and the peasantry. Indeed, the competition for ethnic representation at the centre has been a source of conflict that threatens the very existence of Nigeria. The ultimate power is to preside over the distribution of federal money, allocating licences to oil explorers, and to steal. Religion and ethnicity are manipulated by the key political actors in order to obtain and consolidate this power in Nigeria's Fourth Republic.⁴⁰

This politics of ethnicity and religion has given birth to bad governance. Since 1999 till date, things have not changed. General Muhammadu Buhari who came with

37. See Akinyele, "Ethnicity, Religion".

38. See Alade Fawole, "Military Rule and the Unitarianisation of Nigeria", in R.A. Olaniyan (ed.), *The Amalgamation and its Enemies*, 149-165.

39. See Falola, *The Toyin Falola Reader*, 479.

40. See for instance, Olufemi Vaughan, "Sharia Politics, the 1999 Constitution and the Rise of the Fourth Republic", in A. Carl Levan and Patric Ukata (eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of Nigerian Politics* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2018), 239-256. See also, A. Agbaje, A. Akinde and J. Ojo, "The Peoples Democratic Party: From the 1999 Transition to the 2015 Turnover", in A. Carl Levan and Patrick Ukata (eds.), *The Oxford Handbook*, 351-365.

the “Change Mantra” in 2015 and the “Next Level” in 2019 could not change the situation before he left office in May 29, 2023.⁴¹ Currently, Nigeria’s democracy is in crisis. Onanuga avers that “we are all victims of Nigeria’s bad governance, and we all experience its symptoms in one form or the other”.⁴² These symptoms include; failed educational system, comatose health care, insecurity, dysfunctional government, unemployment, erratic power supply, among others. They all point to the helplessness and inability of government to do well in these areas.⁴³ The rate of poverty is so high, to the extent that, about “133 million Nigerians are multi-dimensionally poor”. Onanuga cited in M.O. Okotoni, “Government Crisis and State Failure in Nigeria: Are we All Guilty?” Inaugural Lecture Series 299 delivered at OAU, Ile-Ife, Osun State, 14 th March, 2017, 1-6. Today, in Nigeria, people are poorer and angrier. Public corruption has become a big challenge to good governance. It has become the bane of politics in Nigeria. It has been argued that the current travails of the country on political and economic fronts are due chiefly to its pervasive public corruption. Acemoglu and Robinson argue that there is a strong connection between political and economic institutions.⁴⁴ The duo argue further that extractive political institution gives power to a narrow, selfish elite and places little encumbrance on the exercise of such power. Economic institution, therefore, is then structured by this selfish; narrow and parochial elite to extract resources from the rest of the society. The result is underdevelopment, which Nigeria has been battling with in this Fourth Republic.

5. Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

By way of conclusion, this paper has examined ethno-religious issues in Nigerian politics in this current Fourth Republic. It argues that the Nigerian political class has employed the two totems for their selfish ends. The ultimate end is to secure the political power. And this has not helped Nigeria as far as nation-building and development are concerned. Obviously, ethnicity and religion are not the real problems facing the Nigerian state.⁴⁵ It is the weaponisation or politicisation of the two by the political elite that has taken the country to where it is today. Ethnicity and religion have served and are still serving Nigerian politics as bargaining devices, by members of diverse groups to negotiate and compromise.⁴⁶ To get out of the woods, the paper, therefore, recommends the following:

Nigeria needs good leadership. A good leader with clear visions, who is willing

41. For more on this, see The Punch, “Nigeria Losing the Battle against Poverty”. Available @<https://punchng.com/Nigeria-losing-the-battle-against-poverty> (accessed 27-6-22).

42. See for instance, Olufemi Vaughan, “Sharia Politics, the 1999 Constitution and the Rise of the Fourth Republic”, in A. Carl Levan and Patric Ukata (eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of Nigerian Politics* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2018), 239-256. See also, A. Agbaje, A. Akinde and J. Ojo, “The Peoples Democratic Party: From the 1999 Transition to the 2015 Turnover”, in A. Carl Levan and Patrick Ukata (eds.), *The Oxford Handbook*, 351-365.

43. For more on this, see The Punch, “Nigeria Losing the Battle against Poverty”. Available @<https://punchng.com/Nigeria-losing-the-battle-against-poverty> (accessed 27-6-22).

44. See Matthew A. Aderoju, “Good Governance: A Pathway to Sustainable National Development in Nigeria”. *GVU Journal of Language, Literature and African Studies*, 1 (1), (2022), 136-156.

45. See Akinyele, “Ethnicity, Religion”, 141-142.

46. For instance, see Toyin Falola, (ed.), *African Politics in Post-imperial Times: The Essays of Richard Sklar* (Trenton, New Jersey: Africa World Press, 2002), 491-502.

and ready to change the status quo. In this regard, the process of choosing leaders at the various levels of the Nigerian state needs review. Imposition of leaders rather than allowing people to choose their own leader should be rejected. This will bring about the emergence of genuine leaders who are not self-seeking or selfish.

Moreover, building and maintaining state institutions capable of regulating the conduct of political elite would also be of help. The existing institutions, like the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) and Independent Corrupt Practices and Related Offences Commission (ICPC), must be adequately funded and strengthened.

Moreover, the current economic situation in the country has made the people to be susceptible to manipulation by the political elite, who weaponise ethnic and religious sentiments. Based on this, all governmental policies should target poverty alleviation.

In addition, Nigeria as a country needs to build strong institutions. What drives a state is the legal, institutional and regulatory framework. There are crises and agitations everywhere, feelings of marginalisation and exclusion, a rise in political and criminal violence, among others. Strong institutions would help in this direction. Nigeria needs new people-driven constitution to move forward.

Finally, there is a need to revisit the restructuring of the federation. A restructured entity is one legacy this generation can and ought to bequeath to the generations yet unborn. It is incumbent on us to create a more perfect administratively and more meaningful union that conforms to basic tenets of federalism to drive socio-economic development in Nigeria. In other words, there must be devolution of power to the federating units instead of centralisation of power at the centre. Nigeria is a natural federation, and it must be seen as such.